

The Effects of Piper nigrum Soaking Temperature, Density, and Sacking on its Stiffness Measured Using our Tailor Made Pepper Stiffness Instrument

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Abstract: This study aims to measure the effects of Piper nigrum soaking temperature, density, and sacking on its stiffness using our tailor-made Piper nigrum stiffness instrument. The soaking water temperature is classified as low (room water temperature), moderate (60 °C), and high temperature (90 °C). The Piper nigrum density is grouped into low (90 gr/2 l), moderate (90 gr/1.5 l), and high density (90 gr/1 l). The Piper nigrum is divided into sacking and non-sacking. The experiment is conducted in three batches. Hence, the total samples are 54 (3 x 3 x 2 x 3). The first batch (18 samples) is divided into three temperature groups, three density groups, and two sacking groups. The second and third samples of temperature groups are treated further with moderate or high temperatures, respectively, for five minutes. The first batch is lifted from the soaking tubs for natural drying. These processes are repeated for the second and third batches. The stiffness measurements, from 11352.56 N/m to 20356.32 N/m, were obtained. The results tested using three-way Anova with a 5 % (0.05) significance level (95 % confidence level) showed that there were significant interactions among Piper nigrum soaking temperature, density, and sacking on its stiffness.

Keywords: density; Piper nigrum pericarp stiffness; Piper nigrum stiffness instrument; sacking; soaking temperature

1. Introduction

Energy is vital to increasing the quality of Piper nigrum. All processes in producing Piper nigrum products need energy¹. These roles are valid for both traditional and modern processing systems that use many controllers inside². The soaking process in this paper is one example of energy saving when producing Piper nigrum products. Piper nigrum, the king of spices³, is very useful for traditional Indonesian medicine to cure various ailments⁴, such as an antioxidant and anti-inflammatory^{5,6}. There are some kinds of Piper nigrum, but the most famous are the black Piper nigrum (black gold)⁷ and the white Piper nigrum. The main feature that differentiates white and black Piper nigrum is the existence of their pericarp, which influences their piperine content⁸. Unlike the black Piper nigrum⁹, the white Piper nigrum¹⁰ has no pericarp. The pericarp is considered a significant determinant of colour intensity, texture and yield of Piper nigrum¹¹. Its pericarp

is intentionally thrown away, usually by soaking it. Hence, the efficiency of producing white Piper nigrum is lower than that of black Piper nigrum¹², typically 25-28 % compared to 33-37 %¹³. At the same quantity, the piperine percentage for white Piper nigrum in Lampung, Indonesia, is typically higher than that of black Piper nigrum¹⁴. The removal of the Piper nigrum pericarp can be done with chemical, physical, or biological methods¹⁵. The majority (99.9%) of pepper plantations in Indonesia are smallholder plantations¹⁶, so the famous method, especially in Indonesia, is using a soaking process. The retting method is defined as the fibre extraction that involves decomposition by the microbiological method of the cementing material or dissolution by chemical method in which the fibre bundles are loosened from the adhering tissues and extracted by washing¹⁷. This process generally takes a time that is too long, 10-14 days¹⁸. Therefore, the chemical, physical, and biological methods are combined to accelerate the soaking process. For example, the soaking

process is combined with boiling¹⁹). Alternatively, adding some organisms, such as bacteria, especially *Bacillus subtilis*²⁰).

The soaking process is usually carried out in rivers²¹). This habit is risky both for the workers, the *Piper nigrum* itself, and the river. The workers might be swept away by a sudden flood, especially in big rivers. Rivers are usually dirty and polluted, and unneeded materials in the river water may contaminate the *Piper nigrum*. On the other hand, the decomposed material from the *Piper nigrum* can pollute the river water, particularly in the aspects of turbidity, pH, dissolved oxygen, and chemical oxygen demand²²), and reduce the colour quality²³). Durian waste husks can be used as an adsorbent to improve soaking water during the retting process of *piper nigrum*²⁴). This technique, however, is not suitable for soaking in rivers.

In order to avoid soaking in rivers, The Development of Integrated Farming System in Upland Areas (UPLAND) Project has developed some soaking tubs in Purbalingga Regency, Central Java Province, Indonesia 1). So far, unfortunately, there are no records showing that the utilization of soaking tubs can improve the *Piper nigrum* quality measured from the hardness aspect. The golden goal for the soaking process is to reduce the hardness of the *Piper nigrum* pericarp. Therefore, the *Piper nigrum* pericarp can be peeled off easily to make the white *Piper nigrum*.

There are several factors that influence the hardness of *Piper nigrum* pericarps, including temperature, density (concentration), soaking time, sacking, additional acid material, bacteria, and mechanical flow. This study aims to obtain the effects of *Piper nigrum* soaking temperature, density, and sacking on its hardness. However, the authors prefer to use stiffness for this study for some reasons, which will be explained later. The dependent variable was measured using our tailor-made pepper stiffness instrument. Hardness refers to the resistance of a material to deformation or penetration²⁵). Especially on the sacking aspect, this study can answer the research question of whether soaking tubs are beneficial or not in reducing the *Piper nigrum* pericarp.

There are some famous methods to measure material hardness, such as Vickers, Brinell, Rockwell, Knoop, and Berkovich²⁶). These methods are usually used for non-organic materials such as metal and plastic, some of which are made in portable form²⁷⁻²⁹). The hardness tester is also used for organic materials such as fruits³⁰). The hardness tester for fruits can be measured based on a texture analyzer³¹) and tactile method^{32,33}). So far as the authors know, however, there is no method dedicated to measuring the hardness of *Piper nigrum* pericarp, especially after the soaking process. So, for this study, the authors also developed a *Piper nigrum* pericarp hardness instrument first.

The common hardness testers are based on the force on a

certain area. So, even though there are many hardness unities, they can be converted into Newton/m². Our tailor-made *Piper nigrum* hardness instrument works based on the displacement that reacts to the force that works on that object (*Piper nigrum* in this case). This instrument is dedicated to this purpose to the common hardness testers, but their unity is different. Our instrument has a unity Newton/m. Hence, as many of our tailor-made instruments are in control^{34,35}), measurement^{36,37}), and software³⁸), the *Piper nigrum* stiffness instrument also has a special purpose. To avoid misunderstanding hardness in Newton/m², the authors use the word stiffness, the ratio of load to deflection Newton/m³⁹).

2. Methodology

2.1. Data Gathering

2.1.1. Experiment Process

Some preparations (Figure 1) are made before conducting the main activity in this study, namely the *Piper nigrum* pericarp stiffness as a function of temperature, density, and sacking. Generally, stiffness and compression characteristics are extremely important parameters for size reduction operations⁴⁰). In this study, it is an important parameter for producing white *Piper nigrum*. The preparation includes raw material procurement, soaking, washing, heating (boiling), and draining.

We have to prepare the raw material, namely the *Piper nigrum*. Mature and ripe pepper berries are used for white pepper production due to the stiffness of the peppercorn and thinner outer skin⁴¹). For this sake, the *Piper nigrum* was picked directly from the *Piper nigrum* field in Purbalingga. This method was also used to reduce the possibility of *Piper nigrum* damage due to the transportation process via a freight forwarding agent. Before the soaking process, the branches, leaves, and dirt of *Piper nigrum* should be thrown away first. This activity should be carried out because white pepper is of better quality if the stalk is removed first⁴²). The pericarp, stalks, and leaves of *Piper nigrum* are usually treated as waste materials^{43,44}).

The utilization of mechanical tools has the potential to damage the *Piper nigrum* berries⁴⁵). Hence, the *Piper nigrum* farmers tend to use soaking techniques rather than

Fig. 1: Experiment process

mechanical tools. The soaking was conducted for six days. After soaking, the Piper nigrum was washed slightly. This action was to make sure that the Piper nigrum was clean. Some Piper nigrum were heating. The heating was classified into two groups, 60 °C and 100 °C. Water was heated at 60 °C or 100 °C. Then, the Piper nigrum was poured into the heated water for 5 minutes.

All Piper nigrum should be drained first. So, there was no flowing or dripping water from the Piper nigrum tube. In this phase, the Piper nigrum pericarp stiffness was ready to be measured.

2.1.2. Measurement Process

In this study, Piper nigrum stiffness cannot be measured using a common stiffness tester, but a special one is needed (Figure 2) for some reasons. 1) There is a variation in the ripe fruit stiffness of Piper nigrum(46). So, the measurement stiffness of Piper nigrum can not be represented by a single berry. The Piper nigrum pericarp would also like to be measured in the collection of fruit after they experience the soaking process.2) The stiffness measurement is also dependent on the face sheet(47), which, in this study, is not as flat as the common objects.

All Piper nigrum that has been drained has become almost dry. The almost dry Piper nigrum then was weighed first. Its weight should be made uniformly at 90 gr and a distance of 10 cm. Then, it was entered into the Piper nigrum tube. Shake the tube slightly so the Piper nigrum berries are in their proper positions. Place the piston surface into the Piper nigrum surface in the Piper nigrum tube. Measure the distance of the piston canopy using a laser distance meter (LDM, a handheld device that uses a laser beam to measure the distance between the Piper nigrum surface and the piston canopy) to obtain the initial measurement.

Lift the piston. Lock the piston canopy so it cannot move up and down. Place the load into the piston canopy centre. Drop the piston with its load into the Piper nigrum surface in the Piper nigrum tube. Remeasure the distance of the piston canopy using the LDM to obtain the final measurement.

Subtract the first distance measurement with the second distance measurement. The distance difference (length) is proportional to the compression experienced by the Piper

Fig. 3: The flowchart of the measurement process.

nigrum in the Piper nigrum tube. The flowchart of all these processes is presented in Figure 3.

The design of the stiffness instrument for this study is available on the patent of this paper(48). Hence, there is no further discussion in this paper.

The stiffness instrument in this study is a new one. Therefore, it cannot be calibrated directly using its standard. What should be conducted is by calibrating its factors. Two dominant variables that influence the stiffness of the instrument were mass and distance. These units can be calibrated at a formal calibration laboratory. The calibration result shows that a 1000 g mass was calibrated to 1020.47, with an error of 2.047%. The accuracy of LDM was 1.5 mm for the range of 40 m, or the LDM accuracy was 0.00375 %. It can be seen that the mass error is much higher than the distance error. Hence, the accuracy of this stiffness instrument is around 2%.

2.2. Data Analysis

2.2.1. Stiffness conversion

The deformation modulus expresses the stiffness of the material in N/m(42). In this study, however, the stiffness is stated as N/m(49) following the international system for units, where if the force uses Newton (N), then the distance uses a meter (m).

The distances were then converted into stiffness by dividing the force by the distance. Hence, stiffness is inversely proportional to the displacement measurement.

2.2.2. Anova

Anova (analysis of variance) is a statistical technique for analyzing mean differences(50). The Anova used in this study is a three-way Anova with a 5 % significance level (95 % confidence level) and many parameters.

The total sum of squares is

$$SST = \sum_{n=1}^n X_n^2 \tag{1}$$

The treatment sum of squares is

$$SST_r = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{tdsb})^2}{n} \tag{2}$$

Fig. 2: Measurement process

The error sum of squares is equal to the total sum of squares minus the treatment sum of squares⁵¹⁾ Hence it is represented as:

$$SSE = SST - SST_r \tag{3}$$

The temperature sum of squares is

$$SSE_t = \frac{(\sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1sb})^2}{n_t} + \frac{(\sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2sb})^2}{n_t} + \frac{(\sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3sb})^2}{n_t} - SST_r \tag{4}$$

The density sum of squares is

$$SSE_d = \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1sb})^2}{n_d} + \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2sb})^2}{n_d} + \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3sb})^2}{n_d} - SST_r \tag{5}$$

The sacking sum of squares is

$$SSE_s = \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{d=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{tds1b})^2}{n_s} + \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{d=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{tds2b})^2}{n_s} - SST_r \tag{6}$$

The temperature and density interaction sum of squares is

$$SSE_{td} = \frac{(\sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1sb})^2}{n_{sb}} + \frac{(\sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2sb})^2}{n_{sb}} + \frac{(\sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3sb})^2}{n_{sb}} + \frac{(\sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1sb})^2}{n_{sb}} + \frac{(\sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2sb})^2}{n_{sb}} + \frac{(\sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3sb})^2}{n_{sb}} + \frac{(\sum_{s=1}^2 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3sb})^2}{n_{sb}} - SST_r - SSE_t - SSE_d \tag{7}$$

The temperature and sacking interaction sum of squares is

$$SSE_{ts} = \frac{(\sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1sb})^2}{n_{db}} + \frac{(\sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2sb})^2}{n_{db}} + \frac{(\sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3sb})^2}{n_{db}} + \frac{(\sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1sb})^2}{n_{db}} + \frac{(\sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2sb})^2}{n_{db}} + \frac{(\sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3sb})^2}{n_{db}} - SST_r - SSE_t - SSE_s \tag{8}$$

The density and sacking interaction sum of squares is

$$SSE_{ds} = \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1sb})^2}{n_{tb}} + \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2sb})^2}{n_{tb}} + \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3sb})^2}{n_{tb}} + \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1sb})^2}{n_{tb}} + \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2sb})^2}{n_{tb}} + \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3sb})^2}{n_{tb}} - SST_r - SSE_d - SSE_s \tag{9}$$

The temperature, density and sacking interaction sum of squares is

$$SSE_{tds} = \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1s1b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1s2b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2s1b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2s2b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3s1b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3s2b})^2}{n_b} - SSST_r - SSE_t - SSE_d - SSE_s \tag{10}$$

$$\frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2s2b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3s1b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3s2b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1s1b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1s2b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2s1b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2s2b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3s1b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3s2b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1s1b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td1s2b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2s1b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td2s2b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3s1b})^2}{n_b} + \frac{(\sum_{b=1}^3 X_{td3s2b})^2}{n_b} - SSST_r - SSE_t - SSE_d - SSE_s \tag{10}$$

The internal sum of squares is

$$SSE_i = SSE - (SSE_t + SSE_d + SSE_s + SSE_{td} + SSE_{ts} + SSE_{ds} + SSE_{tds}) \tag{11}$$

The total number of degrees of freedom

$$DF_{tot} = n_{tot} - 1 \tag{12}$$

The temperature number of degrees of freedom

$$DF_t = n_t - 1 \tag{13}$$

The density number of degrees of freedom

$$DF_d = n_d - 1 \tag{14}$$

The sacking number of degrees of freedom

$$DF_s = n_s - 1 \tag{15}$$

The temperature vs density number of degrees of freedom

$$DF_{td} = (n_t - 1)(n_d - 1) \tag{16}$$

The temperature vs sacking number of degrees of freedom

$$DF_{ts} = (n_t - 1)(n_s - 1) \tag{17}$$

The density vs sacking number of degrees of freedom

$$DF_{ds} = (n_d - 1)(n_s - 1) \tag{18}$$

The temperature vs density vs sacking number of degrees of freedom

$$DF_{tds} = (n_t - 1)(n_d - 1)(n_s - 1) \tag{19}$$

The internal number of degrees of freedom

$$DF_i = DF_{tot} - (DF_t + DF_d + DF_s + DF_{td} + DF_{ts} + DF_{ds} + DF_{tds}) \tag{20}$$

There are three kinds of mean squares, namely the main effect, interaction, and internal mean squares. The main effect means square consists of temperature (MS_t), density (MS_d), and sacking (MS_s) mean squares. The interaction

means squares comprise the interaction between temperature and density (MS_{td}), temperature and sacking (MS_{ts}), density and sacking (MS_{ds}), and among temperature, density, and sacking (MS_{tds}). Another main square, called the total mean square is no longer used for further calculation. Hence, it is not presented in the following formulas.

$$MS_t = \frac{SSE_t}{DF_t} \tag{21}$$

$$MS_d = \frac{SSE_d}{DF_d} \tag{22}$$

$$MS_s = \frac{SSE_s}{DF_s} \tag{23}$$

$$MS_{td} = \frac{SSE_{td}}{DF_{td}} \tag{24}$$

$$MS_{ts} = \frac{SSE_{ts}}{DF_{ts}} \tag{25}$$

$$MS_{ds} = \frac{SSE_{ds}}{DF_{ds}} \tag{26}$$

$$MS_{tds} = \frac{SSE_{tds}}{DF_{tds}} \tag{27}$$

$$MS_i = \frac{SSE_i}{DF_i} \tag{28}$$

2.2.3. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is obtained by comparing the experiment F (F_e) values with statistic (theoretical, F_s) F (Fisher-Snedecor). In this study, there are seven null hypotheses (Hypothesis 1 – Hypothesis 7). The seven hypotheses are:

Water temperature has no significant effect on the stiffness of *Piper nigrum* pericarp.

Tub density has no significant effect on the stiffness of *Piper nigrum* pericarp.

Pepper sacking has no significant effect on the stiffness of *Piper nigrum* pericarp.

There is no significant interaction between water temperature and tub density that affects the stiffness of *Piper nigrum* pericarp.

There is no significant interaction between water temperature and *Piper nigrum* sacking that affects the stiffness of *Piper nigrum* pericarp.

There is no significant interaction between tub density and *Piper nigrum* sacking that affects the stiffness of *Piper nigrum* pericarp.

There is no significant interaction among water temperature, tub density, and *Piper nigrum* sacking that affects the stiffness of *Piper nigrum* pericarp.

There are two kinds of F_e values, namely the main effect and interaction F values. The main effect F_e value consists of the mean square comparisons between the temperature

and internal ($F_{eDF_t:DF_i}$), density and internal ($F_{eDF_d:DF_i}$), and sacking and internal ($F_{eDF_s:DF_i}$). The interaction F_e comprises the mean square comparisons between temperature and density interaction and internal ($F_{eDF_{td}:DF_i}$), temperature and sacking interaction and internal ($F_{eDF_{ts}:DF_i}$), density and sacking interaction and internal ($F_{eDF_{ds}:DF_i}$), and temperature, density, and sacking interaction and internal ($F_{eDF_{tds}:DF_i}$).

$$F_{eDF_t:DF_i} = \frac{MS_t}{MS_i} \tag{29}$$

$$F_{eDF_d:DF_i} = \frac{MS_d}{MS_i} \tag{30}$$

$$F_{eDF_s:DF_i} = \frac{MS_s}{MS_i} \tag{31}$$

$$F_{eDF_{td}:DF_i} = \frac{MS_{td}}{MS_i} \tag{32}$$

$$F_{eDF_{ts}:DF_i} = \frac{MS_{ts}}{MS_i} \tag{33}$$

$$F_{eDF_{ds}:DF_i} = \frac{MS_{ds}}{MS_i} \tag{34}$$

$$F_{eDF_{tds}:DF_i} = \frac{MS_{tds}}{MS_i} \tag{35}$$

The magnitude of F_s is obtained from the F table that is usually available in many inferential statistic books. Two things make the magnitude of F_s usually different. These are the row effect and column effect on the F table. The row effect depended on the DF of the main effect and interaction effect. The column effect is caused only by the internal DF.

Each of the hypotheses will be accepted based on the following formulas:

$$F_{eDF_t:DF_i} \leq F_{s2:36} \tag{36}$$

$$F_{eDF_d:DF_i} \leq F_{s2:36} \tag{37}$$

$$F_{eDF_s:DF_i} \leq F_{s1:36} \tag{38}$$

$$F_{eDF_{td}:DF_i} \leq F_{s4:36} \tag{39}$$

$$F_{eDF_{ts}:DF_i} \leq F_{s2:36} \tag{40}$$

$$F_{eDF_{ds}:DF_i} \leq F_{s2:36} \tag{41}$$

$$F_{eDF_{tds}:DF_i} \leq F_{s4:36} \tag{42}$$

If the correct F_s is not obtained on the F table, then a linear interpolation is carried out from the two nearest values. For example, there is no DF= 36 for the column of the F table (Table 1).

Table 1: Interpolation for DB= 36 on the column of the F table

$F_{e1:36}$	$F_{s1:30}$	$F_{s1:40}$	$F_{s1:36}$	$F_{e2:36}$	$F_{s2:30}$	$F_{s2:40}$	$F_{s2:36}$	$F_{e4:36}$	$F_{s4:30}$	$F_{s4:40}$	$F_{s4:36}$
Experiment Result (ER)	250	251	250.6	ER	19.46	19.47	19.467	ER	5.74	5.71	5.728

Table 2: The stiffness measurement results

Temperature (t)	Density (d)	Sacking (s ₁)				Not Sacking (s ₂)	
		X_n or X_{tdsb}		X_n or X_{tdsb}		X_n or X_{tdsb}	
Low (t1) (30 °C)	d1	X1111	X1112	X1113	X1121	X1122	X1123
		19677.78	15136.75	17888.89	13118.52	13416.67	12560.28
	d2	X1211	X1212	X1213	X1221	X1222	X1223
		13118.52	13416.67	15954.95	13416.67	16866.67	15136.75
	d3	X1311	X1312	X1313	X1321	X1322	X1323
		15954.95	17362.75	17362.75	14758.33	12833.33	16866.67
Moderate (t2) (60 °C)	d1	X2111	X2112	X2113	X2121	X2122	X2123
		20356.32	11352.56	17362.75	13728.68	15535.09	13118.52
	d2	X2211	X2212	X2213	X2221	X2222	X2223
		16398.15	16398.15	17888.89	12560.28	14758.33	11806.67
	d3	X2311	X2312	X2313	X2321	X2322	X2323
		12047.62	11575.16	12833.33	12833.33	13118.52	14055.56
High (t3) (100 °C)	d1	X3111	X3112	X3113	X3121	X3122	X3123
		15136.75	15954.95	20356.32	15954.95	13728.68	14398.37
	d2	X3211	X3212	X3213	X3221	X3222	X3223
		12047.62	17362.75	17362.75	16866.67	13728.68	13728.68
	d3	X3311	X3312	X3313	X3321	X3322	X3323
		14398.37	17362.75	15869.18	13728.68	13728.68	14055.56

So far, we have presented the methodology for data gathering (experiment process and measurement process) and data analysis. Then, the data obtained from the experiment process and measurement process are further analyzed and discussed in the result and discussion section. Seven answers will be obtained because there are also seven research questions presented in the hypothesis form. The seven answers to the hypothesis, however, are summarized in one sentence in the conclusion.

3. Result and discussion

3.1. Result

Based on the methodology explained before, stiffness measurement results were obtained and presented in Table 2. Totally there were 54 (3 x 3 x 2 x 3) samples, which were classified by three kinds of temperature (low, moderate, and high), three kinds of density (low, moderate, and high), two kinds of sackings (sacking and not sacking), and three batches (batch 1, batch 2, and batch 3). Hence, the X_n (sample) can be written in general form as X_{tdsb} or in detail from X1111 to X3323.

The raw data in Table 2 was analyzed in squared form, as presented in Table 3. Every row and column in this table were summed using either the column-to-row or row-to-column methods. In this case, both methods gave the same result.

Table 2 was also summed horizontally or vertically (Table 4). The low, moderate, or high temperature was presented

as X1dsb, X2dsb, and X3dsb, respectively, where each X_n has 18 samples. The low, moderate, or high density was presented as Xt1sb, Xt2sb, and Xt3dsb, respectively, where each X_n has 18 samples. The sacking or not sacking was presented as Xtd1b and Xtd2b, respectively, where each X_n has 27 samples. The interaction between temperature and density was presented as X11sb, X12sb, X13sb, X21sb, X22sb, X23sb, X31sb, X32sb, and X33sb, respectively, where each X_n has 6 samples. The interaction between temperature and sacking was presented as X1d1b, X1d2b, X2d1b, X2d2b, X3d1b, and X3d2b, respectively, where each X_n has nine samples. The interaction between density and sacking was presented as Xt11b, Xt12b, Xt21b, Xt22b, Xt31b, and Xt32b, respectively, where each X_n has nine samples. The interaction among temperature, density, and sacking was presented as X111b, X112b, X121b, X122sb, X131b, X132b, X211b, X212b, X221b, X222sb, X231b, X232b, X311b, X312b, X321b, X322sb, X331b, and X332b, respectively where each X_n has three (triplicated) samples. The magnitude of these samples is saved in Table 4.

Some results were obtained (Table 5) by applying formulas presented in the methodology to Table 4. Six hypotheses presented in Table 5 were accepted from seven hypotheses, and two hypotheses were rejected. Hence, there was a significant interaction between water temperature, tub density, and Piper nigrum sacking that affected the stiffness of Piper nigrum pericarp.

Table 3: The stiffness measurement results

Tem perat ure (t)	Den sity (d)	tds 1b	Sacking (s ₁)			$\sum x$	td s ₂ b	Not Sacking (s ₂)			$\sum X$	Grand Total
			Xn					Xn				
Low (t ₁) (30 ° C)	d1	3	X1111	X1112	X1113	3	3	X1121	X1122	X1123	9	270965
			387214	2291212	3200123			1720955	1800069	1577607		
			938.27	65.25	45.68			28.12	44.44	26.32		
	d2	3	X1211	X1212	X1213	3	9	X1221	X1222	X1223	270965	270965
			172095	1800069	2545605			1800069	2844844	2291212		
			528.12	44.44	87.61			44.44	44.44	65.25		
	d3	3	X1311	X1312	X1313	3	9	X1321	X1322	X1323	270965	270965
			254560	3014649	3014649			2178084	1646944	2844844		
			587.61	17.34	17.34			02.78	44.44	44.44		
$\sum X$		9	138710	7105931	8760378	40050	5699108	6291858	6713664	870463	270965	
			54.01	27.03	50.63	2031.6	75.34	33.33	36.02	144.6	176.3	
						7						
Mod erate (t ₂) (60 ° C)	d1	3	X2111	X2112	X2113	3	9	X2121	X2122	X2123	9	379758
			414379	1288807	3014649			1884767	2413389	1720955		
			838.82	11.70	17.34			14.14	50.45	28.12		
	d2	3	X2211	X2212	X2213	3	9	X2221	X2222	X2223	270965	270965
			268899	2688992	3200123			1577607	2178084	1393973		
			262.69	62.69	45.68			26.32	02.78	77.78		
	d3	3	X2311	X2312	X2313	3	9	X2321	X2322	X2323	270965	270965
			145145	1339844	1646944			1646944	1720955	1975586		
			124.72	07.71	44.44			44.44	28.12	41.98		
$\sum X$		9	828424	5317643	7861717	21463	5109318	6312428	5090515	165122	379758	
			226.22	82.10	07.46	60315.	84.91	81.34	47.87	6314.12	6629.9	
						78					1	
High (t ₃) (100 °C)	d1	3	X3111	X3112	X3113	3	9	X3121	X3122	X3123	9	429304
			229121	2545605	4143798			2545605	1884767	2073131		
			265.25	87.61	38.82			87.61	14.14	73.38		
	d2	3	X3211	X3212	X3213	3	9	X3221	X3222	X3223	270965	270965
			145145	3014649	3014649			2844844	1884767	1884767		
			124.72	17.34	17.34			44.44	14.14	14.14		
	d3	3	X3311	X3312	X3313	3	9	X3321	X3322	X3323	270965	270965
			207313	3014649	2518307			1884767	1884767	1975586		
			173.38	17.34	35.09			14.14	14.14	41.98		
$\sum X$		9	581579	8574904	9676754	24067	7275217	5654301	5933485	188630	429304	
			563.34	22.29	91.24	45476.	46.20	42.42	29.49	0418.11	5894.9	
						88					9	
Grand Total	27		139136.	2223874	2099847	69536	126966.1	1808364	1825858	540798	123615	
			09	843.57	931.42	07824	2	506.45	857.10	9876.93	97701.	
						.33					26	

Table 5 had seven main results, which answered the seven hypotheses presented before. The discussion below is based on these results.

3.2. Discussion

The temperature did not affect the stiffness decrement of the Piper nigrum pericarp (the second row of Table 4). At a glance, this result was strange. Due to degradation temperature⁵², the temperature can soften the Piper nigrum pericarp. So, why are both results different? After six days of soaking process, the Piper nigrum pericarp was soft. Besides, the Piper nigrum pericarp is very thin, around 1

mm. Hence, as soon as the Piper nigrum pericarp is soft, heating or boiling for 5 minutes will not soften the Piper nigrum. This result is because the Piper nigrum pericarp has been removed, and what is left is dominated by the hard pepper core, which is why there was no significant difference in heating the soaking water for 5 minutes. It can be seen (the third row of Table 4) that the density did not affect the stiffness decrement of the Piper nigrum pericarp. Due to water absorption⁵³ of materials, It is already known that stiffness decreases with the increase in moisture content⁵⁴. This statement is the reason why Piper nigrum farmers conduct a soaking process to soften the

Piper nigrum pericarp. Based on this finding, the lower the density, the softer the Piper nigrum pericarp. However, the density comparison among 90 gr/1 l, 90 gr/1.5 l, and 90 gr/2l are almost similar.

The sacking did not significantly decrease the stiffness of the Piper nigrum pericarp (the fourth row of Table 4). The reason is that the soaking and washing processes had caused some of the Piper nigrum pericarp to peel off before its stiffness was measured.

There was no interaction between temperature and density that affected the stiffness decrement of Piper nigrum pericarp (the fifth row of Table 4). This is due to the measurement results, which show that temperature or density had no significant effect as an independent variable.

There was no interaction between temperature and sacking in affecting the stiffness decrement of the Piper nigrum pericarp (the sixth row of Table 4). This statement is due to the measurement results, which show that temperature had no significant effect on the Piper nigrum pericarp.

There was no interaction between density and sacking in affecting the stiffness decrement of the Piper nigrum pericarp (the seventh row of Table 4). This statement is due to the measurement results, which show that density had no significant effect on the Piper nigrum pericarp.

There was a significant interaction among temperature, density, and sacking in affecting the stiffness decrement of Piper nigrum pericarp (the eighth row of Table 4).

Table 4: The stiffness measurement results

Tem perat ure (t)	Den sity (d)	td s1 b	Sacking (s1)				Td s 2b	Not Sacking (s2)			Grand Total	
			Xn	$\sum X$				Xn	$\sum X$			
Low (t1) (30 ° C)	d1	3	X1111	X1112	X1113	27878.2.85	3	X1121	X1122	X1123	153223.0788	125559.7684
			19677.78	15136.75	17888.89	52703.42	13118.52	13416.67	12560.28	39095.47	91798.8877	
	d2	3	X1211	X1212	X1213	26881.7.83	3	X1221	X1222	X1223	139948.4346	128869.4002
			13118.52	13416.67	15954.95	42490.14	13416.67	16866.67	15136.75	45420.09	87910.2256	
	d3	3	X1311	X1312	X1313	26074.5.52	3	X1321	X1322	X1323	134766.8556	125978.6606
			15954.95	17362.75	17362.75	50680.45	14758.33	12833.33	16866.67	44458.33	95138.7785	
$\sum X$	9	48751.25	45916.16	51206.59	14587.4.0041	9	41293.52	43116.67	44563.70	128973.8877	274847.8918	
Mod erate (t2) (60 ° C)	d1	3	X2111	X2112	X2113	49071.63	3	X2121	X2122	X2123	42382.29	91453.9194
			20356.32	11352.56	17362.75	49071.63	13728.68	15535.09	13118.52	42382.29	91453.9194	
	d2	3	X2211	X2212	X2213	50685.19	3	X2221	X2222	X2223	39125.28	89810.4689
			16398.15	16398.15	17888.89	50685.19	12560.28	14758.33	11806.67	39125.28	89810.4689	
	d3	3	X2311	X2312	X2313	36456.12	3	X2321	X2322	X2323	40007.41	76463.5232
			12047.62	11575.16	12833.33	36456.12	12833.33	13118.52	14055.56	40007.41	76463.5232	
$\sum X$	9	48802.09	39325.88	48084.97	13621.2.9320	9	39122.30	43411.94	38980.74	121514.9795	257727.9115	
High (t3) (100 ° C)	d1	3	X3111	X3112	X3113	51448.03	3	X3121	X3122	X3123	44082.01	95530.0400
			15136.75	15954.95	20356.32	51448.03	15954.95	13728.68	14398.37	44082.01	95530.0400	
	d2	3	X3211	X3212	X3213	46773.11	3	X3221	X3222	X3223	44324.03	91097.1403
			12047.62	17362.75	17362.75	46773.11	16866.67	13728.68	13728.68	44324.03	91097.1403	
	d3	3	X3311	X3312	X3313	47630.29	3	X3321	X3322	X3323	41512.92	89143.2146
			14398.37	17362.75	15869.18	47630.29	13728.68	13728.68	14055.56	41512.92	89143.2146	
$\sum X$	9	41582.75	50680.45	53588.24	14585.1.4329	9	46550.30	41186.05	42182.61	129918.9620	275770.3949	
Grand Total	27	139136.09	135922.48	152879.80	42793.8.37	27	126966.12	127714.65	125727.05	380407.83	808346.1982	

Cite: S. Wijonarko et al., "The Effects of Piper nigrum Soaking Temperature, Density, and Sacking on its Stiffness Measured Using our Tailor Made Pepper Stiffness Instrument". Evergreen, 13 (02) 738-749 (2026). <https://doi.org/10.5109/7429619>.

Table 5: The summary of hypotheses results with $p < 0.05$

Source	DF	The sums of squares (SS)	The mean squares (MS)	$F_{eDF:36}$	< or >	$F_{eDF:36}$	Hypothesis
Temperature (t)	2	11471776.72	5735888.36	2.085	<	19.47	Accepted
Density (d)	2	9070538.95	4535269.48	1.648	<	19.47	Accepted
Sacking (s)	1	41836152.09	41836152.09	15.205	<	250.6	Accepted
Temperature & density (td)	4	21392926.27	5348231.57	1.944	<	5.73	Accepted
Temperature & sacking (ts)	2	135368.51	67684.25	0.025	<	19.47	Accepted
Density & sacking (ds)	2	11788076.58	5894038.29	2.142	<	19.47	Accepted
Temperature, density, & sacking (tds)	4	66414163.09	16603540.77	6.034	>	5.73	Rejected
Internal (i)	36	99052104.48	2751447.35				
Total (tot)	53	261161106.70	4927568.05				

The effect of sacking was so strong that there was an interaction affecting the stiffness decrement of Piper nigrum pericarp.

Interaction is a situation where the effect of one independent variable on the dependent variable depends on the level of another independent variable⁵⁵. In this case, the impact between two independent variables (temperature and density, temperature and density, density and sacking) was not strong enough to affect the stiffness of Piper nigrum. After the three independent variables interacted together, their impact was significant. This statement is in line with the fact that temperature, density, and density affect each other.

At a glance, almost all the above results were counterintuitive. By observing the Piper nigrum pericarps after they were soaked for six days, it was clear that many parts of the Piper nigrum pericarps peeled off. Therefore, what was measured was not solely the pericarp hardness, but rather the combination of the pericarp and seeds.

To prove the assumption of the effect of the Piper nigrum pericarps peeled off on the stiffness measurement result, a simpler experiment was conducted. The simplification method was chosen because it is not always easy to obtain good Piper nigrum samples, especially during the Piper nigrum season. Two bundles of Piper nigrum berries were tested. The one bundle comprised of fresh Piper nigrum berries. The other bundle were fresh Piper nigrum berries that were boiled for five minutes. Then the hardness of both Piper nigrum bundles was tested.

Figure 4 shows that the hardness of the boiled Piper nigrum bundle was lower than that of the one that was not boiled at all. This result is in agreement with the theory and serves as evidence that strengthens the above assumption, namely, the prolonged soaking has changed the stiffness of Piper pericarp due to the impact of the seed emergence.

Another experiment was conducted. There were three groups of Piper nigrum bundles. Each group represented a sample of low, moderate, and high density. The samples

Fig. 4: The stiffness measurement results of fresh vs boiled Piper nigrum

Fig. 5: The stiffness of Piper nigrum as a function of low, moderate, and high density

were soaked for three days.

Figure 5 shows that the higher the density, the lower the stiffness of the Piper nigrum pericarps. This result aligns with the expected outcome.

The additional experiments yielded different results compared to the main experiment. This fact was due to many parts of the Piper nigrum pericarp being peeled off in the main experiment, whereas in the additional experiments, the Piper nigrum pericarp remained intact. In normal conditions, the interaction between two

independent variables (temperature and density, temperature and sacking, and density and sacking) and among three independent variables (temperature, density, and sacking) would affect the stiffness decrement of *Piper nigrum* pericarp. The reality, as observed in the main experiment, did not support this claim. The more the emergence of seeds - that much harder than pericarps – the higher the measurements of the stiffness.

4. Conclusion

Based on the above discussion, two conclusions can be drawn as follows:

If the soaking has not peeled off the pericarp bundles, then the independent variables affected the stiffness measurement of *Piper nigrum* pericarp bundles in a regular manner, such as the higher the water temperature, the lower the stiffness measurement of *Piper nigrum* pericarp bundles.

In case the soaking of *Piper nigrum* bundles has caused some parts of the *Piper nigrum* pericarp to peel, the stiffness measurement of *Piper nigrum* pericarp bundles might give unexpected results. A lower water temperature, for example, might show lower stiffness measurements of the *Piper nigrum* pericarp bundles, because the measurements of pericarp bundles were unexpectedly replaced with the measurements of the pericarps and their seeds

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